

Whole-genome sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* strain H24 with broad-spectrum antifungal activity isolated from a saline soil in El Bayadh, Algeria

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Abstract

We report the whole genome sequencing (WGS) of a *Bacillus velezensis* strain H24; isolated from a saline soil (locally known as sabkha) in the northwestern region of Algeria; exhibiting *in vitro* biocontrol potential against various plant pathogens. Whole genome sequencing represents a valuable and efficient strategy to gain a glimpse into the key genes responsible for their biocontrol activity. The genome of *B. velezensis* H24 was assembled to a total size of 3.98 Mb, distributed across 90 contigs with an N50 of 2,086,483, and a GC content of 46.36%. The genomic sequence was deposited in NCBI GenBank under the BioProject [PRJNA1332706](#). These data will provide insight into the mechanisms underlying the antagonistic activity of *B. velezensis* H24, a crucial step toward future applications.

Introduction

Chemical pesticides are commonly used to control plant diseases. However, the use of such agents has become a matter of public concern due to their harmful effects on human health as well as the environment (Bempah *et al.*, 2012; Kumar *et al.*, 2019; Abubakar *et al.*, 2020). Microbial pesticides, as biological pathogen control, have emerged as a valuable and environmentally friendly alternative. Therefore, it is a necessity to search for bacteria with broad-spectrum antagonistic effects. *B. velezensis* is considered a safe microorganism and has received considerable attention as a promising biocontrol agent (Fira *et al.*, 2018; Hashem *et al.*, 2019; Bonaterra *et al.*, 2022; Yang *et al.*, 2024). It is well known that this species can produce a variety of antimicrobial compounds (Cyclic lipopeptide, PKS compounds, Bacteriocin, Hydrolytic enzymes), making it a good candidate for future agricultural research (Keswani *et al.*, 2020; Miljaković *et al.*, 2020). In our previous work, we reported the *B. velezensis* strain H24, isolated from saline soil, as a promising antagonistic strain. This bacterial strain exhibited antifungal broad-spectrum activity and was able to produce several hydrolytic enzymes (Ghozlani *et al.*, 2025).

The development of sequencing technologies has proven to be a helpful approach to characterize the genetic traits as well as to explore the molecular mechanisms behind these complex biological processes (Li *et al.*, 2020; Larena *et al.*, 2023). The current study presents the complete annotated genome of the *B. velezensis* strain H24, which can serve as a resource to scrutinise the genome of this potential biocontrol candidate.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

Strain H24 was isolated from the sabkha of El Bayadh in Algeria (Ghozlani *et al.*, 2025).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

This procedure encompassed several steps. Bacteria preparation and DNA processing were conducted following MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>). Subsequent library preparation, DNA sequencing, and bioinformatics were carried out by MicrobesNG. Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions with the following modifications: input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol. Reads were adapter-trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature

The Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) calculator (Yoon *et al.*, 2017) was used to classify the strain precisely. This tool was employed to determine the OrthoANIu percentage between the strain H24 and the reference genome strain *B. velezensis* FZB42 (ASM1578v2; GCF_000015785.2). Additionally, the taxonomic nomenclature was confirmed *via* the PubMLST.org website (Jolley *et al.*, 2018).

Results

Genomic Features

The genomic features of the *B. velezensis* strain H24 are summarized in Table 1. The genome of this strain was estimated at 3,982,678 bp after assembly. The genomic GC content is 46.36 %, while 3804 protein-coding genes were predicted.

Data availability

The complete genome sequence of *B. velezensis* strain H24 has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under the accession numbers listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Genomic features of the *Bacillus velezensis* strain H24 isolated from saline soil of El Bayadh (Algeria).

Bacterial species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
Strain	H24
Genome size (bp)	3,982,678
% GC	46.36
Number of contigs (≥ 1000 bp)	17
Largest contig (bp)	2,086,483
Mean coverage (X)	154.767
Number of reads	1,294,516
N50 (bp)	2,086,483
CDS	3,804
tRNA number	84
tmRNA number	1
SRA accession numbers	SRR35552197
Assemblies accession numbers	JBRKJM000000000

Taxonomic classification

The taxon identification of the H24 strain is based on the ANI values (98.41%) and the MLST taxonomic nomenclature (Table 2).

Table 2: Taxonomic identification of Strain *Bacillus velezensis* H24.

Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy
SPECIES	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota > Bacilli > Bacillales > Bacillaceae > Bacillus > Bacillus velezensis</i>

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are available prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact FN (fnateche@usthb.dz)

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References

- Abubakar, Y., Tijjani, H., Egbuna, C., Adetunji, C.O., Kala, S., Kryeziu, T.L., Ifemeje, J.C., Patrick-Iwuanyanwu, K.C., 2020. Pesticides, History, and Classification, in: Natural Remedies for Pest, Disease and Weed Control. Elsevier, pp. 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819304-4.00003-8>
- Bankevich, A., Nurk, S., Antipov, D., Gurevich, A.A., Dvorkin, M., Kulikov, A.S., Lesin, V.M., Nikolenko, S.I., Pham, S., Prjibelski, A.D., Pyshkin, A.V., Sirotkin, A.V., Vyahhi, N., Tesler, G., Alekseyev, M.A., Pevzner, P.A., 2012. SPAdes: a new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *Journal of Computational Biology* 19, 455–477. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cmb.2012.0021>
- Bempah, C.K., Asomaning, J., Boateng, J., 2012. Market basket survey for some pesticides residues in fruits and vegetables from Ghana. *Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Food Sciences* 2(3), 850–871. <https://office2.jmbfs.org/index.php/JMBFS/article/view/7131>
- Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M., Usadel, B., 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2114–2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>
- Bonaterra, A., Badosa, E., Daranas, N., Francés, J., Roselló, G., Montesinos, E., 2022. Bacteria as biological control agents of plant diseases. *Microorganisms* 10, 1759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10091759>
- Fira, D., Dimkić, I., Berić, T., Lozo, J., Stanković, S., 2018. Biological control of plant pathogens by *Bacillus* species. *Journal of Biotechnology* 285, 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2018.07.044>
- Ghozlani, A., Driss, F., Nguyen, DH., Boumerdassi, H., El Aichar, F., Djouadi, LN., Oliveira, PH., Fardeau, ML., Pradel, N., Rouis, S., Frikha-Gargouri, O., Nateche, F., 2025.

- Bacillus paralicheniformis* strain H12 from saline soil for the management of gray mold in cherry tomatoes. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology* 41(10):386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11274-025-04629-8>
- Hashem, A., Tabassum, B., Fathi Abd_Allah, E., 2019. *Bacillus subtilis*: A plant-growth promoting rhizobacterium that also impacts biotic stress. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 26, 1291–1297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2019.05.004>
- Jolley, K.A., Bray, J.E., Maiden, M.C.J., 2018. Open-access bacterial population genomics: BIGSdb software, the PubMLST.org website and their applications. *Wellcome Open Res* 3, 124. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.14826.1>
- Keswani, C., Singh, H.B., García-Estrada, C., Caradus, J., He, Y.-W., Mezaache-Aichour, S., Glare, T.R., Borriss, R., Sansinenea, E., 2020. Antimicrobial secondary metabolites from agriculturally important bacteria as next-generation pesticides. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 104, 1013–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-019-10300-8>
- Kumar, V., Kumar, P., Singh, J., 2019. Contaminants in Agriculture and Environment: Health Risks and Remediation, in: *Contaminants in Agriculture and Environment: Health Risks and Remediation*. Agriculture and Environmental Science Academy, Haridwar, India, pp. 1–301. <https://doi.org/10.26832/AESA-2019-CAE>
- Larena, I., Espeso, E.A., Veloso, J., 2023. Editorial: impact of novel omic technologies on biological control against plant pathogens. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 14, 1162422. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1162422>
- Li, Z., Song, C., Yi, Y., Kuipers, O.P., 2020. Characterization of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria from perennial ryegrass and genome mining of novel antimicrobial gene clusters. *BMC Genomics* 21, 157. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-020-6563-7>

- Miljaković, D., Marinković, J., Balešević-Tubić, S., 2020. The significance of *Bacillus spp.* in disease suppression and growth promotion of field and vegetable crops. *Microorganisms* 8, 1037. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8071037>
- Pimentel, D., 1996. Green revolution agriculture and chemical hazards. *Science of the Total Environment* 188 Suppl 1: S86-98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-9697\(96\)05280-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-9697(96)05280-1)
- Seemann, T., 2014. Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2068–2069. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu153>
- Yoon, S.-H., Ha, S., Lim, J., Kwon, S., Chun, J., 2017. A large-scale evaluation of algorithms to calculate average nucleotide identity. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 110, 1281–1286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-017-0844-4>
- Zaller, J.G., 2020. Daily poison: pesticides - an underestimated danger. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50530-1>